

Reaction of Triethyl Orthoformate with Amides

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Triethyl orthoformate reacts with both aldehydes and ketones to form a diethyl acetal¹. The reaction is usually carried out in the presence of a catalyst. Reactions between triethyl orthoformate and hydroxy carboxylic acids in equimolar ratios in benzene have been investigated by Narain and Mehrorta². Roberts and co-workers³ used aromatic amines to react with triethyl orthoformate in the presence of a catalytic amount of hydrochloric acid to give the corresponding formimidates.

In the present investigation the author studied the reaction of triethyl orthoformate with few amides, benzamide, acetamide, urea, and thiourea. Attempts were made to prepare a heterocyclic compound by reaction between urea or thiourea with triethyl orthoformate.

Heating the amides with triethyl orthoformate in equimolar ratios, in an oil bath, gave a good yield of the substituted N-amide derivatives, $R-CO-N=CH-OC_2H_5(I)$. The reaction went smoothly and without the use of a catalyst except in the case of urea, when a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid activated the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL*

N-Ethoxymethylene benzamide. ($I, R=C_6H_5$)—A mixture of benzamide (0.1M), and triethyl orthoformate (0.1 M) was placed in a 250 ml. R. B. flask, fitted with a reflux condenser. The flask was heated in an oil bath at 130-140° for 3 hrs. until a solid product was formed. The flask was allowed to cool and the solid product was filtered and washed with ether. The product was extracted twice with boiling ethanol to remove unchanged benzamide. Crystallisation of the product from dimethylformamide-ethanol mixture gave N-methyleneethyl ether of benzamide in white needles (2.5 g., 15.5%), m.p. 239°. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 6.9; N, 8.9. $C_{10}H_{11}ON$ requires: C, 74.5; H, 6.8; N, 8.7%).

N-Ethoxymethylene acetamide ($I, R=CH_3$) was prepared from acetamide as above (3.0 g., 26.1%) m.p. 270°. (Found: C, 52.0; H, 7.9; N, 12.4. $C_5H_9O_2N$ requires: C, 52.2; H, 7.8; N, 12.2%).

N-Ethoxymethylene urea. ($I, R=NH_2$)—A mixture of urea (0.1M), triethyl orthoformate (0.1 M) and 2 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was heated in a similar way.

*Melting points are not corrected. The analysis was carried out by Alfred Bernhardt, Max-Planck Institute, Mulheim (Ruhr), Germany.

1. L. Claisen, *Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 1005; 1898, **31**, 1020.

2. R. P. Narain and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **12**, 538.

3. Roberts and Hussein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1950.

The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from water in yellow needles (6.0 g., 51.7%), m.p. 232°. (Found: C, 41.1 ; H, 6.8; N, 24.6. $C_4H_8O_2N_2$ requires: C, 41.4; H, 6.9; N, 24.2%.)

N-Ethoxymethylene thiourea prepared in the same manner, gave yellow crystals from benzene-acetone (3.0 g., 23.0%), m.p. 160-2°. (Found: C, 36.1; H, 6.4; N, 21.4. $C_4H_8ON_2S$ requires: C, 36.4; H, 6.1; N, 21.2%.)

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